

Deliverable D1.7 Technology Ontology Mapping and Search API Integration for the Euro-BioImaging Access Portal

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
EAP	Euro-BioImaging Access Portal
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FBbi	Biological Imaging Methods Ontology
IDR	Image Data Resource
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
SDCM	Spinning Disk Confocal Microscopy
UI	User Interface
SSBD	Systems Science of Biological Dynamics

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the completion of Task 1.4 and Task 1.5, which aimed to improve semantic interoperability and technology-related image data discoverability within the Euro-BioImaging Access Portal (EAP).

Task 1.4 established mappings between Euro-BioImaging imaging technologies and standardized FBbi ontology terms, creating a harmonized metadata layer for supported technologies.

Task 1.5 implemented a Search Application Programming Interface (API) integration on the EAP that dynamically retrieves representative sample images and associated metadata for technologies with valid ontology mappings.

Both functionalities have been successfully deployed to the production EAP and are available to all users. The implementation improves discoverability, FAIR compliance, and provides a richer user experience through standardized technology descriptions and visual examples, and links Euro-BioImaging technologies with relevant datasets in public repositories.

1. Introduction

The Euro-BioImaging Access Portal (EAP, www.eurobioimaging-access.eu) is the primary access point for researchers seeking imaging technologies and services across the Euro-BioImaging infrastructure. It is a visible and significant focal point in the imaging community in Europe and beyond.

To improve interoperability with the Global Image Data Ecosystem and better align the portal with FAIR principles of image data sharing and discoverability, the FoundingGIDE project identified the need to:

- map the imaging technology terminology on EAP to the established standardized ontology for imaging technologies used and developed for image data in FoundingGIDE,
- integrate external image data repository search capabilities into the EAP,
- enable users browsing technologies on the EAP to see and access image data acquired with said technologies from relevant international image databases.

This deliverable summarizes the implementation and deployment of these functionalities.

2. Description of work

This deliverable summarizes the implementation activities performed under Task 1.4 and Task 1.5 to improve semantic interoperability and content discoverability within the Euro-BioImaging Access Portal.

The work consisted of establishing mapping between Euro-BioImaging imaging technology terminology and the FBbi ontologies. FBbi is a structured controlled vocabulary of sample preparation, visualization and imaging methods used in biomedical research (<https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/FBbi>) and adopted in the FoundingGIDE project. The long-term sustainability and active maintenance of the FBbi ontology, which ensures these mapped terms remain current and resolvable beyond the project's lifespan, is detailed in Deliverable D5.2.¹ The mapping was followed by the integration of a search Application Programming Interface (API) capable of retrieving image data from public databases (such as BioImage Archive), based on these mappings. Together, these developments create a richer and more standardized presentation of imaging technologies while supporting interoperability with external resources and future FAIR data initiatives. They link imaging technologies (that Euro-BioImaging provides open access to) to relevant image data, allowing scientists and company users to explore sample data acquired with the technologies they are interested in. This will enhance understanding of imaging and its possibilities, help users acquire better quality data, as they can see reference data, and provide users with linkages to other relevant studies and data, metadata, image analysis methods etc.

The resulting functionality has been successfully deployed to the production version of EAP and is available for technologies that have validated ontology mappings, providing users with standardized technology descriptions and representative sample images and image data directly within the EAP service pages. The functionality has not yet been implemented for all technologies, as some have no mapped ontology term, the closest term is generic (e.g. “microscopy”), or the mapping process is still ongoing (for instance for newer technologies). However, the functionality is fully ready and in use, and its coverage will be expanded continuously as new sample data and ontology updates become available.

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Currently, a next generation version of the EAP is under development, and it will eventually replace the current production version. The new functionality described here has already been built into the new version of the portal as well, ensuring that it will continue to be available without interruptions once the portal changes, and enabling seamless further development of these features.

2.1. Task 1.4 – Technology Ontology Mapping

Objective

The objective of this task was to establish semantic mappings between technologies available in the Euro-BioImaging Access Portal and standardized ontology resources, specifically FBbi Imaging.

Activities Performed

The implementation included:

- review of technology names on the EAP,
- identification of corresponding ontology concepts in FBbi,
- validation of ontology mappings,
- integration of ontology identifiers into the Access Portal data model and the user interface.

In this work, experts from multiple areas were engaged, including ontology developers, the EAP developers, and the Euro-BioImaging Hub moderators that have the best overall understanding of the Euro-BioImaging nomenclature and have led previous work with international Expert Groups defining this nomenclature. Mappings were created only when a reliable semantic correspondence could be established, ensuring high-quality and accurate metadata representation. Once the mapping was first done on separate spreadsheet files, the EAP database was modified to include “FBBI Terms” for every ratified Euro-BioImaging technology. The EAP user interface was then modified to display these FBbi terms on the EAP technology description pages (Figure 1).

Originally, it was planned that the nomenclature used on the EAP could be modified to match the FoundingGIDE (FBbi) ontology. However, as the work progressed, this was seen as not suitable, because the FBbi ontology and EAP nomenclature are made for different purposes, with the former focusing on image data repositories and the latter optimized for users to find relevant technology solutions and service providers for their experiments. Therefore, it was decided that a better option was to keep the EAP nomenclature as it is, but to include the mapped FBbi terms in addition.

In the future, the mapping will be periodically reviewed and updated, ensuring its expansion and keeping it up to date. In addition, as the GIDE evolves and grows, the Euro-BioImaging Expert Groups can review the nomenclature and make changes that align the EAP nomenclature and FBbi ontology more and more over time, as feasible. Similarly, we hope that the FBbi ontology can be developed further to include more detailed technology ontologies that are closer to those used by technology providers such as Euro-BioImaging and various imaging facilities across the world. So far, ontologies used in image data repositories do not typically have fully developed coverage of image acquisition technologies. It can also be foreseen that more focus would be addressed towards image data processing and analysis nomenclature, as such services may also be defined in more detail during the future development of Euro-BioImaging and other image analysis service providers.

Implementation

The ontology mappings have been integrated into the production Access Portal and are now used to enrich technology service pages.

This provides:

- improvements for standardized metadata,
- improved interoperability,
- better machine-readable technology descriptions,
- a foundation for future semantic services.

Spinning Disk Confocal Microscopy (SDCM)

Spinning disc confocal microscopy is one of the solutions for routine and high-performance fluorescence live-cell imaging applications. SDCM uses a series of moving pinholes on a disc to scan spots of light, in combination with a high-sensitivity camera to acquire instantaneous optical slices. Since a series of pinholes scans an area in parallel, each pinhole is allowed to hover over a specific area for a longer amount of time than on laser scanning confocals (CLSM) thereby reducing the excitation energy needed to illuminate a sample. Furthermore, cameras (often EMCCDs or sCMOS), typically have quantum efficiencies 2-3x higher than PMTs, so much less laser excitation energy is necessary and that reduces photo-toxicity and photo-bleaching of a sample, making it the preferred system for imaging live cells or organisms when optical slicing is necessary. However, optical sectioning in depth is more limited than in CLSM. This technology can be improved with image scanning mic/pixel reassignment to allow non-diffraction limited images which provide resolutions 100-200nm (check with the lab where these improvements are available).

Example Datasets

FBBI Terms

spinning disk confocal microscopy

<p>ssbd-repos-000452 SSBD:repository</p> <p>No Thumbnail</p> <p>We developed a method to enlarge Dictyostelium discoideum cells by partial cytokinesis inhibition, generating multinucleated yet functional gi...</p>		

Figure 1. Example of an EAP technology page (in this case SDCM) showing the associated FBbi ontology term. The figure is a screen capture from the production EAP. In this case, the Euro-BioImaging technology term has a precise FBbi equivalent (this is not always the case, see Figure 2). The figure also shows representative datasets retrieved through the integrated Search API (see 2.2. and Figure 2).

2.2. Task 1.5 – Search API Integration

Objective

The objective was to connect the Euro-BioImaging Access Portal with the Search API to retrieve representative sample images and associated metadata for mapped imaging technologies.

Activities Performed

The API developed in FoundingGIDE Task 11.2 was first evaluated in detail by the EAP team and the API developers together. Connectivity to the API was then developed into the EAP utilizing the ontology mapping from Task 1.4, and finally the EAP UI was updated to display example datasets obtained through the API on its technology pages. For each dataset, the EAP displays an identifier, source repository, a short description and a thumbnail image (See Figures 1 and 2). The entries are clickable, and clicking on an entry takes the user directly to the corresponding dataset in the corresponding repository. Thumbnails are not available for all datasets (as can be seen also in Figures 1 and 2), but they are displayed whenever available. In the future, the various repositories will hopefully be developed in such a way that most datasets will include thumbnails, as these can be highly relevant in use cases such as these.

To make the dataset display feature as useful as possible for people browsing the EAP, a functionality was developed that allows the first row of the results displayed to be human-curated, if desired. In other words, Euro-BioImaging moderators could choose for each of their technologies, which sample datasets are shown first, and all the other datasets would be shown below these. This would ensure that users see relevant and useful datasets first, and datasets that include thumbnails and are thus more representative and illustrative. In the UI, there is no distinction, and in practice this feature simply sorts the results obtained through the API a little bit, but all datasets are still displayed. Using such a feature would require that the criteria for the selected datasets are clear, fair and transparent. This is typically not yet an issue, as the number of datasets retrieved by the API is rather modest in most cases, but as GIDE grows and more and more (compatibly annotated) data gets deposited into the repositories, this can become more relevant. At that point, some result sorting tools may also need to be implemented in the EAP UI to allow users to browse the example datasets more fluently.

The API is currently able to pull data from the following image data repositories: BioImage Archive, Systems Science of Biological Dynamics (SSBD:repository, SSBD:database) and Image Data Resource (IDR) . From the perspective of the EAP, the source of the data does not matter – as long as it is covered by the API, the EAP can display it. This architecture ensures that the coverage of the system automatically expands as GIDE develops and expands; image data from new sources is automatically displayed in EAP and accessible through it, with no additional modifications needed to the portal.

Implementation

The implementation included:

- development of Search API connectivity,

- automatic querying using ontology mappings from Task 1.4,
- retrieval of representative images and metadata,
- integration into the UI of technology service pages.

The Search API is only activated for technologies with validated ontology mappings, ensuring relevant and accurate results.

User Workflow

When a user visits a technology page on the EAP:

1. The portal identifies the associated ontology mapping.
2. The Search API is queried.
3. Representative sample images are retrieved.
4. Images are displayed directly on the service page.

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Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

In Scanning Electron Microscopy, a focussed beam of accelerated electrons is scanned across the surface of the sample and the scanned and secondary electrons are used to generate the SEM image.

SEM can be used to automatically acquire serial images of different samples, and can be operated under cryo conditions (see cryo-SEM), at room temperature or under heated conditions. SEM only provides images of the surface of the sample, but through methods such as freeze-fracturing, an internal view of the sample can also be revealed in SEM.

Example Datasets

FBBI Terms

microscopy

S-BIAD2376
Bioimage Archive

MERFISH of adult human skin across 114 samples, 22 donors, and 15 anatomic sites. H&E of adult human skin

S-BIAD2324
Bioimage Archive

No Thumbnail

Photon Absorption Remote Sensing (PARS) enables label-free imaging of subcellular morphology by observing biomolecule spec...

S-BIAD2071
Bioimage Archive

We used a previously described intersectional/subtractive approach that allows for simultaneous labeling of Aldh1a1+ with EY...

S-BIAD1733
Bioimage Archive

S-BIAD1671
Bioimage Archive

S-BIAD1602
Bioimage Archive

Figure 2. Example of an EAP technology page (in this case SEM) illustrating the automatic retrieval and presentation of representative datasets from public repositories based on the associated FBBI ontology term. The figure is a screen capture from the production EAP. This example also illustrates

that not all Euro-Biolmaging technology terms have precise equivalents in FBbi (yet), in which case the match may be on a rather generic level, such as here (“SEM” vs. “microscopy”).

2.3. Deployment and Validation

Both tasks have been successfully completed and the results deployed on the Euro-Biolmaging Access Portal production environment, as well as already in its future replacement.

Validation included:

- verification of ontology mappings,
- successful Search API communication,
- rendering of representative images,
- frontend integration testing.

The implemented functionality has been deployed to the production Euro-Biolmaging Access Portal and validated using multiple technology pages, such as those shown in Figures 1 and 2. The validation was done first by the EAP development team, followed by other FoundingGIDE team and Euro-Biolmaging Hub members.

- <https://www.eurobioimaging-access.eu/service/spinning-disk-confocal-microscopy-sdcm>
- <https://www.eurobioimaging-access.eu/service/scanning-electron-microscopy-sem>

3. Results and Impact

The implementation delivers several tangible benefits:

Semantic interoperability

Technology descriptions are aligned with standardized FBbi ontologies.

Improved discoverability

Researchers can more easily identify relevant imaging technologies and associated resources.

FAIR metadata

Ontology mappings improve consistency and machine readability while supporting FAIR principles.

Enhanced user experience

Representative sample images provide visual context and improve understanding of imaging modalities, their data and its processing.

Extensible architecture

The implementation provides a scalable foundation for future ontology mappings and additional Search API integrations.

4. Conclusion

Task 1.4 and Task 1.5 have been successfully completed and deployed within the Euro-BioImaging Access Portal.

The implemented ontology mappings establish a standardized semantic layer based on FBbi ontologies, while the Search API integration dynamically enriches technology pages with representative sample images and allows linking imaging technologies to datasets produced by them.

Together, these developments improve interoperability, metadata quality, data discoverability, and the overall user experience, contributing directly to the objectives of the FoundingGIDE project.

The established new functionality is automatically scalable when new data becomes available through the API, it has features that allow for human moderation if needed to ensure quality, and it is built ready for further future development also in the next generation EAP.